

“ICEBERG PRINCIPLE” AS A STYLISTIC FEATURE OF E. HEMINGWAY’S SHORT STORY “THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA”**Dushatova Shokhsanam Bakhtiyorjon qizi**

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Abstract. *The purpose of the work is to identify the stylistic features of the work of E. Hemingway "The Old Man and the Sea" and to consider their functioning in the work. The tasks of the work can be formulated as follows: to consider the typical features of the language style of E. Hemingway; reveal the essence of concepts: inner speech, repetition, "iceberg principle"; consider the main classifications of inner speech, repetitions; determine the frequency of use of the language style, internal speech, repetition, "principle of the iceberg" in the work of E. Hemingway "The Old Man and the Sea".*

Keywords: *stylistic feature, poetics, academic writing, ellipsis, complex sentences, subtext, inner speech, repetition, "iceberg principle".*

«ПРИНЦИП АЙСБЕРГА» КАК СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРИЗНАКА РАССКАЗА Э. ХЕМИНГУЭЯ «СТАРИК И МОРЕ»

Аннотация. *Цель работы – выявить стилистические особенности произведения Э. Хемингуэя «Старик и море» и рассмотреть их функционирование в произведении. Задачи работы можно сформулировать следующим образом: рассмотреть типичные черты языкового стиля Э. Хемингуэя; раскрыть сущность понятий: внутренняя речь, повторение, «принцип айсберга»; рассмотреть основные классификации внутренней речи, повторов; определить частотность употребления языкового стиля, внутренней речи, повторения, «принципа айсберга» в произведении Э. Хемингуэя «Старик и море».*

Ключевые слова: *стилистический признак, поэтика, академическое письмо, эллипсис, сложноподчиненные предложения, подтекст, внутренняя речь, повтор, «принцип айсберга».*

INTRODUCTION

The study of the work of any writer is impossible without referring to his biography, which helps to understand the origins of creativity, the nature of the work, and the features of poetics. Revealing the biography of E. Hemingway, the researchers cite the following facts:

Ernest Miller Hemingway was born in Oak Park, Illinois on July 21, 1899. As a boy, Hemingway spent most of his time in northern Michigan, where he wrote some of his early work. After graduating from high school in 1917, he became a reporter for the Kansas City Star newspaper, where he learned academic writing. He took part in the First World War (1914-1918), becoming a volunteer ambulance driver, fighting in Italy.

He later served as a correspondent for the Toronto Star before settling in Paris. After 1927, Hemingway lived for a long time in Key West, Florida, Spain and Africa. During the Spanish Civil War, he returned to Spain as a newspaper correspondent. During World War II, he again became a correspondent and later a reporter for the United States First Army. After the war, E. Hemingway settled near Havana, Cuba, and in 1958 moved to Ketchum, Idaho. E. Hemingway suffered from severe dementia, probably due to the many drugs he took to suppress

his high blood pressure in old age. It began to seem to him that the US federal authorities were ready to lure him into a trap in order to put him in prison later. In the early morning of July 2, 1961, after repeated failed suicide attempts, E. Hemingway died after shooting himself in the head with a hunting rifle.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

E. Hemingway's "The Old Man and the Sea" (1952) earned him the 1953 Pulitzer Prize for Fiction. "The Old Man and the Sea" was also hailed as a masterpiece. This novel earned Hemingway the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1954 [4, 35]. E. Hemingway became famous for his unique style of writing. He took many pioneering steps in reforming writing technique, such as emphasizing the use of dialogue rather than narration. He uses "stream of consciousness" or "flashback" in his work and also uses simple sentences while avoiding complex expressions. Hemingway pioneered a simple and new way of writing in English [4, 35]. High literary scholar Peter B. says that Hemingway's sentences are usually short and simple. He rarely uses adjectives. The writer sometimes repeats a key phrase with an ellipsis to emphasize a particular point in the story. Another commentary on E. Hemingway's unique writing style is given by X. J. Kennedy. He notes: "The well-known style of E. Hemingway includes both short sentences and long ones, but when the sentences are long, they tend to be relatively simple in structure. E. Hemingway loves long complex sentences (sentence plus sentence plus sentence), connected by the union "and". Hemingway is a master of fast, short dialogue and often presents entire scenes in the form of a conversation" (Kennedy, 2015: 76).

Striving for brevity and expressiveness, E. Hemingway, already at the initial stage of his creative path, created a technique that he himself called the iceberg principle: "If a writer knows well what he writes about, he can omit much of what he knows, and if he writes truthfully, the reader will feel everything omitted just as strongly as if the writer had said it" (Hemingway, 1961: 177). E. Hemingway explained the "principle of the iceberg" using the story "The Old Man and the Sea" as an example. He had rich knowledge and experience about the sea, about fishing, about fishermen. If he wanted to describe everything he knew about the sea and fishing, he would need thousands of pages of texts. All this knowledge is the underwater part of the iceberg and is reflected in the text. E. Hemingway compared his works with icebergs: "They are seven-eighths submerged in water, and only one eighth of them is visible". The system of hints and defaults in the works of E. Hemingway functions in a similar way. Hemingway's famous "iceberg principle" came about through the observation of details. An important part of this principle is the transmission of secret experience through body language. By describing the body (the visible part of the iceberg, which is a person), we can create an idea of the inner world, that is, the invisible underwater part of the iceberg. "Hemingway's text is 'corporeal' and 'substantial'. Gestures, postures and body movements of his characters are meticulously recorded. Body language is very eloquent – in Hemingway it is frank and much more expressive than words" [3, 83].

The work has two constant components, which are:

1. The text is the visible part of the iceberg, one-eighth of the story written.
2. Subtext - the unwritten part of the story. It contains a great life experience, knowledge, reflections of the writer.

RESULTS

In order to “realize” the subtext, it is necessary to organize prose, create a single system: writer - hero - reader. The visible part of the iceberg is the old man and the sea, a duel between them. In the invisible underwater part of the iceberg, the author's reflections on the problems in life are hidden: man and nature, man and society, man and the Universe. The hero of E. Hemingway is alone against a hostile world. Surrounded by people, the hero always feels lonely, and the world in which he is located is hostile. In the usual dialogue between the old man and the boy, the writer reveals the "guess" of his plan. His story is the fruit of a mature generalization. He explains that man was created in order to suffer defeat, perhaps destruction awaits man, but man himself is invincible.

In his work, critic I. A. Kashkin notes that E. Hemingway “The sharp line between the simple person to whom the writer is attracted, and his own lyrical hero, is erased.” I. A. Kashkin emphasizes that the image of the old man "loses its integrity, but it becomes richer, more diverse" [7, 201]. The old man is not alone at all, he has someone to pass on his skills, and in this sense, “the book is open to the future”: “The family passes, and the family comes, but not only the earth, but also human work remains forever, not only in their own creations of art, but also as a skill passed down from hand to hand, from generation to generation”. In general, according to Kashkin, no one dies in the book, while old age is described on the very threshold of extinction. Victory (moral) is not achieved at the cost of life [8, 296].

CONCLUSION

The writing style of E. Hemingway is the simplicity of language and thought. It is artless and free from conscious literary effort. The writer's style was direct and personal, his images were rich and full-blooded, his words were simple and energetic. The story "The Old Man and the Sea" is widely considered one of the best works of art by E. Hemingway. After he had just written a book, he admitted that it was the best book he could write in his entire life. The language style of this book makes it incredible. Among all Hemingway's works, The Old Man and the Sea is considered the most typical example of the use of the iceberg technique. The literary advantage of using this principle is due to the fact that only 1/8 of it is "above the water". The author rarely expresses his own feelings directly and does not make any comments or explanations. On the contrary, he tries to tell and describe things objectively and combine his feelings in harmony with natural narration and description. This gives readers a condensed picture that each reader builds for themselves.

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